

REALIZING WISHFUL DREAM: TO PREDICT LAMINATE ULTIMATE STRENGTH UPON INDEPENDENT CONSTITUENT PROPERTIES ONLY

Zheng-Ming Huang*, L. Liu

School of Aerospace Engineering & Applied Mechanics, Tongji University
1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, P. R. China

*Corresponding author (huangzm@mail.tongji.edu.cn)

Keywords: *Laminate, failure analysis, strength prediction, Bridging Model, stress concentration factor, matrix in-situ strength*

1. Introduction

A long-term dream in the composite community is to predict the ultimate strength of a laminated composite under arbitrary load only based on the mechanical properties of its constituents measured independently. No commercial FEM (Finite Element Method) software package exists in the market, which can be used to make a failure analysis and an ultimate load sustaining ability estimation with reliable accuracy on a structure containing composite materials without input data of the composites themselves. Undoubtedly, once this dream becomes a reality, an optimized design from bottom constituents up to final structure made of composites can be fulfilled, and more effective and expanded use of composite structures in various fields of engineering can be expected.

In order to achieve this goal, three challenging problems must be resolved with high success. First, the internal stresses in the constituent fiber and matrix materials of each lamina in the laminate subjected to any load must be determined accurately. Second, efficient failure criteria for both the lamina and the laminate based on the known internal stresses in the constituents must be established. Last but not least, input data of all the in-situ properties of the fiber and matrix materials must be explicitly correlated with their mechanical behaviors measured independently.

This author and his group have made systematically efforts to address all of the three problems. The thus established theory, characterized as the Bridging Model, is summarized in this paper. As will be shown subsequently, three important factors to influence the accuracy of a strength prediction for a composite are, respectively, a stress concentration factor (SCF) in the matrix, plastic behavior of the matrix, and thermal residual stresses in the constituents. The theory has been applied to analyze all of the

World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE) problems only using independent fiber and matrix properties provided by the exercise organizers. The overall prediction accuracy is 10% higher than that attained by the most accurate, phenomenological strength theory attended the exercise.

2. Stress Evaluation

An incremental stress-strain relationship in the global coordinate system for the k^{th} lamina with a stacking angle of θ within a laminate is given by (see Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. Definition for a positive lamination angle in global coordinate system of a laminate

$$\begin{aligned} \{d\sigma_i\}^G &= ([T_{ij}]_c)_k ([S_{ij}]_k)^{-1} ([T_{ij}]_c^T)_k \{d\varepsilon_j\}^G \\ &= [(C_{ij}^G)_k] \{d\varepsilon_j\}^G, \end{aligned} \quad (1.1)$$

$$[T_{ij}]_c = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2(\theta) & \sin^2(\theta) & -\sin(2\theta) \\ \sin^2(\theta) & \cos^2(\theta) & \sin(2\theta) \\ \frac{\sin(2\theta)}{2} & -\frac{\sin(2\theta)}{2} & \cos(2\theta) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1.2)$$

where “G” refers to “global”, $\{d\varepsilon_j\}^G = \{d\varepsilon_{xx}^0 + zd\kappa_{xx}^0$

, $d\varepsilon_{yy}^0 + z d\kappa_{yy}^0, 2d\varepsilon_{xy}^0 + 2z d\kappa_{xy}^0 \}^T$ with $d\varepsilon_{xx}^0$, $d\varepsilon_{yy}^0$ and $d\varepsilon_{xy}^0$ and $d\kappa_{xx}^0$, $d\kappa_{yy}^0$ and $d\kappa_{xy}^0$ being the in-plane strain and curvature increments of the middle plane of the laminate, $\{d\sigma_i\}^G = \{d\sigma_{xx}, d\sigma_{yy}, d\sigma_{xy}\}^T$, and $[S_{ij}]$ is an instantaneous compliance tensor of the lamina given by the Bridging Model through^[1-2]

$$[S_{ij}] = (V_f [S_{ij}^f] + V_m [S_{ij}^m] [A_{ij}]) (V_f [I] + V_m [A_{ij}])^{-1} \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), V_f and V_m are the fiber and matrix volume fractions of the composite with $V_f + V_m = 1$. $[I]$ is a unit tensor. $[A_{ij}]$ is an instantaneous bridging tensor. $[S_{ij}^f]$ and $[S_{ij}^m]$ are the instantaneous compliance tensors of the fiber and the matrix materials. In this paper, the fiber is assumed to be linearly elastic until rupture with $[S_{ij}^f]$ given by Hooke's law, whereas the matrix must be considered as elastic-plastic whose instantaneous compliance tensor is specified by Prandtl-Reuss theory. Explicit expressions for $[S_{ij}^m]$ and $[A_{ij}]$ are given in Appendix. More details can refer to, e.g., Refs. [1] and [2]. The in-plane strain and curvature increments are obtained from the following classical laminate theory equations^[1]

$$\begin{Bmatrix} d\Omega_1^I + dN_{xx} \\ d\Omega_2^I + dN_{yy} \\ d\Omega_3^I + dN_{xy} \\ d\Omega_1^{II} + dM_{xx} \\ d\Omega_2^{II} + dM_{yy} \\ d\Omega_3^{II} + dM_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{11}^I & Q_{12}^I & Q_{13}^I & Q_{11}^{II} & Q_{12}^{II} & Q_{13}^{II} \\ Q_{12}^I & Q_{22}^I & Q_{23}^I & Q_{12}^{II} & Q_{22}^{II} & Q_{23}^{II} \\ Q_{13}^I & Q_{23}^I & Q_{33}^I & Q_{13}^{II} & Q_{23}^{II} & Q_{33}^{II} \\ Q_{11}^{III} & Q_{12}^{III} & Q_{13}^{III} & Q_{11}^{IV} & Q_{12}^{IV} & Q_{13}^{IV} \\ Q_{12}^{III} & Q_{22}^{III} & Q_{23}^{III} & Q_{12}^{IV} & Q_{22}^{IV} & Q_{23}^{IV} \\ Q_{13}^{III} & Q_{23}^{III} & Q_{33}^{III} & Q_{13}^{IV} & Q_{23}^{IV} & Q_{33}^{IV} \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} d\varepsilon_{xx}^0 \\ d\varepsilon_{yy}^0 \\ 2d\varepsilon_{xy}^0 \\ d\kappa_{xx}^0 \\ d\kappa_{yy}^0 \\ 2d\kappa_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3.1)$$

$$Q_{ij}^I = \sum_{k=1}^n (C_{ij}^G)_k^1 (z_k - z_{k-1}), \quad (3.2a)$$

$$Q_{ij}^{II} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n (C_{ij}^G)_k^1 (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2), \quad (3.2b)$$

$$Q_{ij}^{III} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^n (C_{ij}^G)_k^1 (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3), \quad (3.2c)$$

$$d\Omega_i^I = \sum_{k=1}^n (\beta_i)_k^G (z_k - z_{k-1}) dT, \quad (3.3a)$$

$$d\Omega_i^{II} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n (\beta_i)_k^G (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) dT, \quad (3.3b)$$

$$\{\beta_i\}_k^G = \{(\beta_1)_k^G, (\beta_2)_k^G, (\beta_3)_k^G\}^T = ([T_{ij}]_c)_k ([S_{ij}]_k)^{-1} \{\alpha_j\}_k \quad (3.4)$$

$$\{\alpha_i\} = V_f ([S_{ij}^f] - [S_{ij}^m]) \{b_j^f\} + V_f \{\alpha_i^f\} + V_m \{\alpha_i^m\}. \quad (3.5)$$

In the above, dN_{xx} , dN_{yy} , and dN_{xy} and dM_{xx} , dM_{yy} , and dM_{xy} are the overall in-plane force and moment increments per unit length (width) applied on the laminate respectively. $dT = T_1 - T_0$, where T_1 is the working (e.g., room) temperature and T_0 is a reference (e.g., curing) temperature at which initial stresses in the fiber and matrix are all known (e.g., zero). $\{\alpha_j^f\}$ and $\{\alpha_j^m\}$ are the thermal expansion coefficient vectors of the fiber and matrix, respectively. $\{b_i^f\}$ is the fiber thermal stress concentration vector given by^[1,2]

$$\{b_i^f\} = \frac{V_m}{V_f} ([I] - [A_{ij}] (V_f [I] + V_m [A_{ij}])^{-1}) ([S_{ij}^f] - [S_{ij}^m])^{-1} \times (\{\alpha_j^f\} - \{\alpha_j^m\}) \quad (4)$$

The averaged stress increments in the global coordinate system shared by the k^{th} lamina can be calculated through Eqs. (1) providing that the strain increments on the right-hand side of Eq. (1.1) is replaced by the following quantities

$$\{d\varepsilon_j\}_k^G = \{d\varepsilon_{xx}^0 + \frac{z_k + z_{k-1}}{2} d\kappa_{xx}^0, d\varepsilon_{yy}^0 + \frac{z_k + z_{k-1}}{2} d\kappa_{yy}^0, 2d\varepsilon_{xy}^0 + (z_k + z_{k-1}) d\kappa_{xy}^0\}, \quad k=1, 2, \dots, n \quad (5)$$

After being transformed into the stresses in the local coordinates through

$$\{d\sigma_i\} = [T_{ij}]_s^T \{d\sigma_j\}^G, \quad (6.1)$$

$$[T_{ij}]_s = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2(\theta) & \sin^2(\theta) & -\sin(2\theta)/2 \\ \sin^2(\theta) & \cos^2(\theta) & \sin(2\theta)/2 \\ \sin(2\theta) & -\sin(2\theta) & \cos(2\theta) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6.2)$$

the internal stress increments in the fiber and matrix of the k^{th} lamina are calculated from^[1,2]

$$\{d\sigma_i^f\} = (V_f [I] + V_m [A_{ij}])^{-1} \{d\sigma_j\} + \{b_i^f\} dT, \quad (7.1)$$

$$\{d\sigma_i^m\} = [A_{ij}] (V_f [I] + V_m [A_{ij}])^{-1} \{d\sigma_j\} + \{b_i^m\} dT, \quad (7.2)$$

$$\{b_i^m\} = ([I] - [A_{ij}] (V_f [I] + V_m [A_{ij}])^{-1}) ([S_{ij}^f] - [S_{ij}^m])^{-1} \times (\{\alpha_j^m\} - \{\alpha_j^f\}) \quad (7.3)$$

Thermal residual stresses in the fiber and matrix can be calculated by simply setting all of the mechanically applied load increments on the left-hand side of Eq. (3.1) to be zero.

Remark. When both the fiber and the matrix are in elastic deformation, the bridging tensor $[A_{ij}]$ is a simplified form from that of the Mori-Tanaka's model, see Ref. [2] for details, but shows higher accuracy for prediction of composite elastic properties^[3]. However, when the matrix as well as fiber can undergo inelastic deformation, the Bridging Model's determination for an instantaneous bridging

tensor $[A_{ij}]$ is unique. As indicated in **Table 4**, the involvement of matrix's plasticity can improve the overall accuracy for ultimate strength predictions to within 10% of experiments by as much as 16%.

In Ref. [4], a pure matrix interface layer was introduced into any two adjacent primary laminae of the laminate, because the two laminae can be considered as being bonded together by the matrix. The introduction of the interface layers was found to have a positive effect on the laminate strength prediction^[4], and is also applied in this paper's prediction. The number of the laminate layers is then increased from N , the original layer number, to $n=2N-1$. All of the above equations are kept unchanged, except that the mechanical properties of the interface layers are taken to be the same as those of the pure matrix^[4]. The thickness of an interface layer is assigned to be 5% of that of a primary lamina^[4]. Keeping the whole thickness and the fiber volume fraction of the laminate as unchanged, the thickness and the fiber volume fraction of each primary layer have to be adjusted accordingly. As shown in **Fig. 2**, the thickness of a mid primary layer is changed from h_0 to $0.95h_0$ whereas the fiber volume fraction is increased from V_f^0 to $\frac{100}{95}V_f^0$.

Further, the thickness of the surface layers is varied from h_0 to $0.975h_0$, with the fiber volume fraction of the surface layers increased from V_f^0 to $\frac{100}{97.5}V_f^0$.

Fig. 2. Schematic of a laminate containing pure matrix interface layers

3. Failure Detection

When either of the fiber and matrix materials in a lamina fails, the lamina is considered to have attained a failure status. An ultimate strength of a laminate is attributed to an ultimate failure of the laminate.

3.1. Failure detection for a fiber

As a fiber material is thin, much resembling a beam

structure, and is mainly used to sustain loads along its axial direction, a generalized maximum normal stress failure criterion^[2] is pertinent to assess a fiber tensile or compressive failure, through the following conditions

$$\sigma_{eq,t}^f \geq \sigma_{u,t}^f, \quad (8.1)$$

$$\sigma_{eq,t}^f = \begin{cases} \sigma_f^1, & \text{when } \sigma_f^3 < 0, \\ [(\sigma_f^1)^q + (\sigma_f^2)^q]^{\frac{1}{q}}, & \text{when } \sigma_f^3 = 0, \end{cases} \quad (8.2)$$

$$\sigma_{eq,c}^f \geq -\sigma_{u,c}^f, \quad (9.1)$$

$$\sigma_{eq,c}^f = \begin{cases} \sigma_f^3, & \text{when } \sigma_f^1 > 0, \\ \sigma_f^3 - \sigma_f^1 & \text{when } \sigma_f^1 \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (9.2)$$

In the above, σ_f^1 , σ_f^2 and σ_f^3 (with $\sigma_f^1 \geq \sigma_f^2 \geq \sigma_f^3$) are the three principal stresses of the fiber due to combined thermal and mechanical loads, $\sigma_{u,t}^f$ and $\sigma_{u,c}^f$ are the fiber tensile and compressive strengths along its axial direction, and q is a power-index ($q=3$ in this paper). It is noted that a reduction or an elevation on the material load carrying capacity due to a multi-axial tension or multi-axial compression is taken into account through Eq. (8.2) or Eq. (9.2), respectively.

3.2. Failure detection for a matrix

Although the maximum or the generalized maximum normal stress failure criterion may be the simplest and most easily applicable, because of only two strength parameters involved, it is less suitable to assess a matrix failure. Two reasons are apparent. First, when the matrix is subjected to either a uniaxial tension or an in-plane shearing, evaluation for the resulting equivalent stress, $\sigma_{eq,t}^m$ (similar to Eq. (8.2)), for the matrix is the same, equal to the externally applied (tensile or shear) stress. However, a matrix material generally has a different tensile from a shear strength. Thus, applying the criterion similar to Eqs. (8) to detect a matrix failure will be in error by nature even under uniaxial tension or in-plane shearing if the matrix strength parameter measured under in-plane shearing or uniaxial tension is specified as $\sigma_{u,t}^m$. Evidently, a possibility of a matrix failure due to a uniaxial tensile load equals to that due to an in-plane shear load. This is different from a fiber material which fails mainly due to axial loads. Second, anisotropy in in-situ strength behaviors of the matrix strongly suggests that a different failure criterion, which contains all of the

ultimate strength parameters for the matrix, should be applied. Many such failure criteria exist in the literature. Let us choose to use Tsai-Wu criterion to do this, which postulates that a matrix failure is attained as long as

$$F_1(\sigma_{11}^m)^2 + F_2(\sigma_{22}^m)^2 + F_3\sigma_{11}^m\sigma_{22}^m + F_4(\sigma_{12}^m)^2 + F_5\sigma_{11}^m + F_6\sigma_{22}^m \geq 1 \quad (10.1)$$

where $F_1 = \frac{1}{XX'}$, $F_2 = \frac{1}{YY'}$, $F_3 = -\sqrt{F_1F_2}$,

$$F_4 = \frac{1}{(S)^2}, F_5 = \frac{X'-X}{XX'}, F_6 = \frac{Y'-Y}{YY'}. \quad (10.2)$$

In Eq. (10.2), X , X' , Y , Y' , and S denote the in-situ axial (along fiber axial direction) tension, axial compression, transverse tension, transverse compression, and in-plane shear strengths of the matrix, respectively. How to determine these strength parameters will be elaborated in the next section.

No failure mode can be recognized with the application of Tsai-Wu criterion. As shown subsequently, a matrix compressive failure will correspond to an ultimate failure of the laminate, whereas a matrix tensile failure will be followed by a stiffness degradation. Thus, one must be sure whether the matrix failure is correspondent to a tensile or compressive failure. Furthermore, to define matrix instantaneous elastic-plastic parameters such as Young's and hardening moduli from either a tensile or a compressive stress-strain curve, one also needs to know whether the matrix is under essential tension or essential compression. To resolve these, let us apply the following condition to identify a load-sustaining mode^[1]

$$\sigma_m^1 + \sigma_m^2 + \sigma_m^3 \geq 0, \text{ matrix is in tension,} \quad (11.1)$$

$$\sigma_m^1 + \sigma_m^2 + \sigma_m^3 < 0, \text{ matrix is in compression,} \quad (11.2)$$

where σ_m^1 , σ_m^2 and σ_m^3 (with $\sigma_m^1 \geq \sigma_m^2 \geq \sigma_m^3$) are the three principal stresses of the matrix, respectively.

3.3. Fatal and nonfatal failure

It has been pointed out in Ref. [4] that among four kinds of failure modes, i.e., the fiber and matrix tensile and compressive failures, only a matrix tensile failure corresponds to a non-fatal failure, which must be followed by a stiffness discount. In other words, as long as there is a fiber tensile or compressive failure or there is a matrix compressive failure occurring in any primary lamina of the laminate, the laminate is considered to have attained a fatal failure. The corresponding load level on the laminate is defined as its ultimate strength, and the simulation procedure is stopped.

3.4. Stiffness discount

This paper also employs the stiffness discount scheme proposed in Ref. [4]. Namely, when a matrix tensile failure occurs at some load level to a lamina, its stiffness at the next incremental load step will be calculated upon degraded moduli (both elastic and hardening moduli) of the matrix. Here, a hardening modulus is a tangent to the stress-strain curve of the matrix in a plastic region. The degradation is carried out through

$$E^m = 0.01E_0^m, \quad (12)$$

where E_0^m is a matrix modulus (elastic or hardening modulus) just before the degradation to take place. The stiffness discount not only affects elastic modulus and hardening one used in Prandtl-Reuss theory in obtaining an instantaneous compliance tensor $[S_{ij}^m]$ (see Appendix), but also influences calculation of the elements of $[A_{ij}]$, thus resulting in discounted $[S_{ij}]$ in Eq. (2). All of the other material parameters including the fiber elastic properties and Poisson's ratio of the matrix are not affected.

3.5. Ultimate failure criterion

Except for fatal failures, an excessively large strain should be classified as an ultimate failure as well. This is because a lamina and hence the laminate may undergo unlimited large deformation after nonfatal failures occur, or, Eq. (12) is applied, continuously. As mentioned in Ref. [4], a typical polymer matrix composite will generally not undergo a strain component in absolute value greater than 12%. Thus, this strain limitation is also served as an ultimate failure condition. For easy reference, the ultimate failure criteria for a laminate are summarized in **Table 1**. It should be realized that any kind of interface failure cannot be considered as an ultimate failure of the laminate, and Eq. (12) is applied whenever an interface failure occurs.

Table 1. Ultimate failure criteria for a laminate

Case	Description
1	A fiber tensile failure occurs in any primary layer
2	A fiber compressive failure occurs in any primary layer
3	A matrix compressive failure occurs in any primary layer
4	Any strain of a primary layer in absolute value is equal to or greater than a critical value (12%)

4. Constituent Property Determination

From an application point of view, the most important task is to define input data of the constituent material properties. While all of the constituent elastic-plastic property parameters can be taken to be those measured independently, the matrix ultimate strengths must be assigned as in-situ values. This is because a transverse tensile strength of a unidirectional (UD) composite is generally much smaller than the tensile strength of its monolithic matrix material. However, it is hardly able to measure an in-situ matrix strength from a composite specimen. How to define the matrix in-situ strengths from its original counterparts remains open in the literature. It is well known that an infinite isotropic plate containing a hole will generate a stress concentration when the plate is subjected to a far-field in-plane load. The maximum stress concentration factor is 3. In other words, the in-situ strength of the plate containing the hole can be as small as one third of that without the hole. Similarly, when the hole is filled with a fiber cylinder, the matrix subjected to a transverse load must undergo a stress concentration. It is this stress concentration that causes the composite transverse tensile strength significantly smaller than what it would be. Thus, the matrix in-situ transverse strength can be defined if a SCF is obtained.

4.1. Stress field in matrix

In order to investigate a stress concentration, the stress field in the matrix embedded with the fiber must be known. We follow the classical approach for the stress concentration in an isotropic plate containing a circular hole^[5]. Consider an infinite isotropic matrix plate having a circular fiber medium in its center. The plate at its infinite boundary is subjected to a uniform load along a chosen, e.g., the x_2 direction, as shown in **Fig. 3** (with $b \rightarrow \infty$). The resulting radial, circumferential, and shear stress components in the matrix material have been obtained by Cheng & Chen in Ref. [6] based on elasticity theory as

$$\sigma_\rho^m = \frac{\sigma_{22}^0}{2} \left\{ 1 + A \frac{a^2}{\rho^2} + \left[1 + B \left(\frac{4a^2}{\rho^2} - \frac{3a^4}{\rho^4} \right) \right] \cos 2\varphi \right\}, \quad (13.1)$$

$$\sigma_\varphi^m = \frac{\sigma_{22}^0}{2} \left\{ 1 - A \frac{a^2}{\rho^2} - \left[1 - B \frac{3a^4}{\rho^4} \right] \cos 2\varphi \right\}, \quad (13.2)$$

$$\tau_{\rho\varphi}^m = -\frac{\sigma_{22}^0}{2} \left\{ 1 - B \left[\frac{2a^2}{\rho^2} - \frac{3a^4}{\rho^4} \right] \right\} \sin 2\varphi, \quad (13.3)$$

$$A = \frac{E^f(1-\nu^m) - E^m(1-\nu^f)}{E^m(1-\nu^f) + E^f(1+\nu^m)}, \quad (13.4)$$

$$B = \frac{E^f(1+\nu^m) - E^m(1+\nu^f)}{E^m(1+\nu^f) + E^f(3-\nu^m)}. \quad (13.5)$$

Fig. 3. A matrix domain embedded with a fiber cylinder subjected to a uniaxial tension

By virtue of a coordinate transformation, the stress component in the x_2 direction is given by

$$\sigma_{22}^m = \sigma_\rho^m \cos^2 \varphi + \sigma_\varphi^m \sin^2 \varphi - \tau_{\rho\varphi}^m \sin 2\varphi \quad (14)$$

It must be pointed out that although the geometry of **Fig. 3** (with $b \rightarrow \infty$) is exactly the model on which the Mori-Tanaka theory was established the basic stress equations (13.1)-(13.5) are for a planar stress problem, which is different in geometry from a RVE (representative volume element) for the UD composite^[4]. To find out stress fields in the fiber and matrix materials of the RVE is a planar strain problem. Due to well known relationship between solutions for a planar stress problem and those for a planar strain one, the stress components in the matrix material of the RVE subjected to a transverse load similar to that shown in **Fig. 3** are also given by Eqs. (13.1)-(13.5), providing that the elastic moduli and Poisson's ratios of both the fiber and the matrix are replaced by the following quantities

$$E_i' = \frac{E^i}{1-(\nu^i)^2}, \quad \nu_i' = \frac{\nu^i}{1-\nu^i}, \quad i=f, m \quad (15)$$

In other words, the constants A and B should be replaced by A' and B' respectively, where

$$A' = \frac{[1-\nu^m - 2(\nu^m)^2]E_{22}^f - [1-\nu_{23}^f - 2(\nu_{23}^f)^2]E^m}{E_{22}^f(1+\nu^m) + E^m[1-\nu_{23}^f - 2(\nu_{23}^f)^2]}, \quad (16.1)$$

$$B' = \frac{E^m(1+\nu_{23}^f) - (1+\nu^m)E_{22}^f}{E_{22}^f[\nu^m + 4(\nu^m)^2 - 3] - E^m(1+\nu_{23}^f)}. \quad (16.2)$$

It is noted that in Eqs. (16.1) and (16.2) the fiber elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio have been replaced by its transverse counterparts, E_{22}^f and ν_{23}^f , respectively^[7].

4.2. Definition of a SCF

Phenomenologically, a SCF should be influenced by three kinds of factors. Firstly, it should be closely related to a loading direction. A longitudinally applied load (i.e., a load along the fiber axial direction) or a transverse load will cause the matrix's SCF to be different. Secondly, a SCF should depend on the fiber and matrix properties. When the fiber becomes the same as the matrix, the SCF will equal to 1; when the fiber property becomes negligible, the SCF will approach 3. Thirdly, a SCF should be a function of the fiber volume fraction of the composite.

In the classical approach, a SCF for an isotropic plate containing a hole subjected to an in-plane load is defined as the maximum stress on the hole surface divided by the externally applied stress^[5]. If we followed this way, i.e., if we divided a stress component on the fiber-matrix interface by the stress applied at the infinite boundary, the resulting SCF would be independent of the fiber volume fraction. Furthermore, the SCF would be infinite if there were a void or debonding between the fiber and the matrix. Thus, the classical definition for a SCF is not applicable to a composite.

Let us first isolate the fiber using a co-axial matrix cylinder (Fig. 3) in such a way that the isolated matrix cylinder containing the fiber is as same as the RVE. In other words, let

$$b = a / \sqrt{V_f}. \quad (17)$$

Next, we calculate an averaged dimensionless stress of σ_{22}^m along a straight line parallel to x_2 axis (Fig. 3) in the matrix domain through

$$K_\varphi^I = \frac{1}{(x_2^b - x_2^a)} \int_{x_2^a}^{x_2^b} \frac{\sigma_{22}^m}{\sigma_{22}^0} \Big|_{x_3=x_3^\varphi} dx_2, \quad (18)$$

where (refer to Fig. 3) $x_2^a = a \cos \varphi$, $x_3^\varphi = a \sin \varphi$, and $x_2^b = \sqrt{b^2 - (x_3^\varphi)^2}$. We then define the first portion of the SCF as

$$K_\varphi^I = \max\{K_\varphi^I, 0^0 \leq \varphi \leq 90^0\} \quad (19)$$

Variations of K_φ^I and $(\sigma_{22}^m / \sigma_{22}^0)$ on the fiber-matrix interface with respect to φ from 0^0 to 180^0 for two

kinds of material systems are shown in Fig. 4. In one of them the fiber used is stiffer whereas in another the fiber is softer than the matrix. It is seen that K_φ^I can assume its maximum value at $\varphi=0^0$ or $\varphi=90^0$ when the fiber is stiffer or softer than the matrix, respectively. If the fiber is stiffer than the matrix, one obtains from Eqs. (18) and (19) that

$$K^I = \frac{1}{(b-a)} \int_a^b \frac{\sigma_{22}^m}{\sigma_{22}^0} \Big|_{\varphi=0^0} dx_2 = 1 + \frac{\sqrt{V_f}}{2} A' + \frac{\sqrt{V_f}}{2} (3 - V_f - \sqrt{V_f}) B'. \quad (20.1)$$

On the other hand, if the fiber is softer than the matrix, one has

$$K^I = \frac{1}{\sqrt{b^2 - a^2}} \int_0^{\sqrt{b^2 - a^2}} \frac{\sigma_{22}^m}{\sigma_{22}^0} \Big|_{\varphi=90^0} dx_2 = 1 - \frac{3V_f}{4} B' - (2A' + 3B') \frac{\tan^{-1} \delta}{4\delta}, \quad \delta = \sqrt{\frac{1}{V_f} - 1}. \quad (20.2)$$

Fig. 4. Variations of K_φ^I and $(\sigma_{22}^m / \sigma_{22}^0)_{\rho=a}$ versus angle φ

In a special case where the fiber's property becomes negligible and $V_f \rightarrow 1$ (i.e., $b \rightarrow a$), one obtains from Eq. (20.2) that $K^I = 3$, which is the classical SCF for an infinite plate containing a circular hole.

It should be pointed out that K^I is a dimensionless stress averaged along only a straight line in the matrix domain of the RVE, whereas a stress component $(\sigma_{22}^m)_{BM}$ obtained by the Bridging Model is an averaged quantity with respect to the whole matrix domain. Therefore, there should be another portion of the SCF if it is applied to the Bridging Model. This second portion is defined as

$$K^{II} = \frac{(\sigma_{22}^m)_{avg}}{(\sigma_{22}^m)_{BM}} = \frac{1}{\pi(b^2 - a^2)(\sigma_{22}^m)_{BM}} \int_a^b \int_0^{2\pi} \sigma_{22}^m \rho d\rho d\varphi$$

It is easy to verify that $(\sigma_{22}^m)_{avg} = \sigma_{22}^0$. Further noticing $(\sigma_{22}^m)_{BM} = a_{22}\sigma_{22}^0/(V_f + V_m a_{22})$, we obtain

$$K^{II} = \frac{(\sigma_{22}^m)_{avg}}{(\sigma_{22}^m)_{BM}} = \frac{(V_f + V_m \beta)E_{22}^f + V_m(1 - \beta)E^m}{\beta E_{22}^f + (1 - \beta)E^m}. \quad (21)$$

The SCF relevant to the stress component in the transverse direction calculated by the Bridging Model is defined as

$$K = K^I \times K^{II}, \quad (22)$$

which equals to the maximum averaged transverse matrix stress along a straight line in RVE obtained from elasticity solution divided by the transverse matrix stress given by the Bridging Model.

4.3. In-situ properties of the matrix

The role of a SCF is to amplify the transverse stress component in the matrix calculated by the Bridging Model. Thus, all of the equations relevant to yielding and failure detections for the matrix should be modified by multiplying the involved σ_{22}^m by the SCF. For instance, a von Mises equivalent stress (see Appendix) is modified to

$$\sigma_e^m = \sqrt{(\sigma_{11}^m)^2 + (K\sigma_{22}^m)^2 - (\sigma_{11}^m)(K\sigma_{22}^m) + 3(\sigma_{12}^m)^2}, \quad (23)$$

whereas the deviatoric stresses of the matrix used in defining $[S_{ij}^m]$ should be changed to

$$\begin{aligned} (\sigma_{11}^m)' &= (2\sigma_{11}^m - K\sigma_{22}^m)/3, & (\sigma_{22}^m)' &= (2K\sigma_{22}^m - \sigma_{11}^m)/3, \\ (\sigma_{12}^m)' &= \sigma_{12}^m. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Furthermore, the quantities in Eq. (10.2) should be replaced, respectively, by

$$\begin{aligned} F_1 &= \frac{1}{\sigma_{u,t}^m \sigma_{u,c}^m}, & F_2 &= \frac{K^2}{\sigma_{u,t}^m \sigma_{u,c}^m}, & F_3 &= -\sqrt{F_1 F_2}, \\ F_4 &= \frac{1}{(S_u^m)^2}, & F_5 &= \frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{\sigma_{u,t}^m \sigma_{u,c}^m}, & F_6 &= K \frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{\sigma_{u,t}^m \sigma_{u,c}^m}, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

where $\sigma_{u,t}^m$, $\sigma_{u,c}^m$, and S_u^m are, respectively, the matrix tensile, compressive, and shear strengths measured using monolithic material specimens or provided independently.

5. Application

To verify the efficiency of the methods especially a SCF formula presented in this paper, let us apply them to re-analyze all of the WWFE problems.

5.1. Input data

Four pairs of fiber and matrix material systems were

used in the exercise, for which necessary mechanical properties together with thermal expansion coefficients have been provided by the organizers^[7]. Processing conditions for the four laminae are re-summarized in **Table 2**. All of the elastic property parameters of the constituent fibers and matrices are directly taken from the original data, and are summarized in **Table 3**. Bridging parameters, β and α , for each material system were previously adjusted in such a way that the predicted transverse and in-plane shear moduli correlated reasonably with the provided counterparts^[8]. In most cases, these bridging parameters can take a value in between 0.35 to 0.45 without calibration. The used bridging parameters are relisted in **Table 2**. Using the parameters of **Tables 2** and **3**, the SCFs for the four matrix materials are calculated as per Eqs. (20.1) and (21). They are given in **Table 2**.

All of the four matrices are considered to have the same mechanical properties under tension and compression except for ultimate strengths, as no difference was mentioned by the organizers. No stress-strain curve for any matrix material has been provided by the organizers. However, the provided in-plane shear stress-strain curves of the four laminae showed significant nonlinearity. They are used to retrieve the plastic property parameters of the corresponding matrix materials. The retrieving has been carried out without application of a SCF. Hence, the retrieved plastic parameters are the same as those used for blind predictions in Ref. [8] and are relisted in **Table 3**. In this way, the first part of a stress concentration factor, i.e. K^I , has been implicitly incorporated into the retrieved plastic parameters. Only the second part of the stress concentration factor, K^{II} , needs to be used in definition or detection of a matrix plastic behavior. In other words, the SCF, K in Eqs. (23) and (24), should be replaced by K^{II} . It is noted that the SCF in Eq. (25) is not influenced.

The most critical mechanical properties of the constituents are their strength values. Whereas a matrix strength (tensile, compressive, or shear strength) can be accurately measured using monolithic material specimens, a fiber strength (tensile or compressive strength) is generally not measured directly upon very thin fiber specimen. Instead, it has most probably been determined through back retrieving. In light of this, both the tensile and compressive strengths of the fibers have been adjusted against the longitudinal tensile and compressive strengths of the corresponding lamina. The adjusted fiber strength parameters are summarized in **Table 3**. Comparing these fiber

strengths with the provided counterparts^[9], generally not larger than 20% between them can be seen. As long as available, any matrix strength is directly taken from the provided data. There is one exception with the LY556 matrix, for which the shear strength was not provided. This strength parameter is determined from retrieving on the corresponding lamina shear strength. The thus obtained matrix strengths are also listed in **Table 3**.

5.2. Failure prediction

Detailed specifications including lamination, loads to be applied, and what kinds of predictions should be made for each of a total number of 14 problems have been provided in Ref. [9]. The present predictions exactly follow those specifications. The predicted results are compared with the available experimental data^[10], the Bridging Model based predictions but with retrieved constituent strengths as input data^[4], and Zinoviev et al.'s predictions^[11] which were accomplished based on a phenomenological strength theory and were judged to be the most accurate among the theories attended the WWFE^[12]. Due to space limitation, plots of correlations between the predicted and the measured results for most of the problems are omitted. However, the comparisons for all of the 14 problems are made quantitatively as per the rules set forth by the exercise organizers^[13], and are summarized in **Table 4**. The scores are mainly consisted of 3 kinds of Grades, i.e., Grade A, Grade B and Grade C, where Grade A denotes a prediction within $\pm 10\%$ of the experimental value, Grade B represents a prediction in between $\pm 10\%$ and $\pm 50\%$ agreement with the measured data, and Grade C stands for a prediction outside $\pm 50\%$ of the experimental value. In the table, "Huang(provided)" refers to the predictions in this paper based on the originally provided data and "Huang(retrieved)" to those made in Ref. [4] using the retrieved properties. As can be seen From **Table 4**, the most significant influencing factor to the prediction of a composite strength is a SCF. Moreover, the incorporation of the matrix plasticity and thermal residual stresses is also important for an accurate prediction of laminate failure behavior and ultimate strength. To show this more clearly, we graph the predictions of different inputs for the E-glass/LY556/HT907/DY063 UD composite (i.e., the second problem in the WWFE) subjected to combined transverse tension or compression and in-plane shear loads against the experimental data^[10] in **Fig. 5**. Five envelopes, all of which have been obtained based on the present method, i.e., based on the originally provided

constituent property parameters, are plotted to show dependence of ultimate strengths on the SCF, matrix plasticity and thermal residual stresses respectively. The figure clearly shows that without applying a SCF, a micromechanical prediction for a composite strength based on its monolithic constituent properties can be untrue. If the matrix plasticity and thermal residual stresses are not taken into account, the predictions can be in error. Without the SCF incorporated, the predicted strengths under tension, compression and shear are 118MPa, -254MPa and 67MPa respectively, even though the matrix plasticity and thermal residual stresses are taken into account. On the other hands, those strengths are 37MPa, -122MPa and 60 MPa, respectively, if all of the three influencing factors, i.e., the SCF, the matrix plasticity, and the thermal residual stresses are incorporated. The stress ratios for these two cases are $118/37 > -254/-122 > 67/60$. In other words, the most significant influence of a SCF is on the predicted transverse tensile strength of a UD composite, then on the transverse compressive strength, and least on the in-plane shear strength. This is attributed to two reasons. First, the involvement of a SCF affects not only the stress component induced by a mechanical load, but also the thermal residual stress in the matrix. In the present case, the thermal residual stresses are positive (tensile), thus giving rise to a tensile failure more easily than a compressive failure. Second, the role of a SCF is merely to magnify the transverse stress component in the matrix. When an in-plane shear load is applied to the UD composite, only the transverse thermal residual stress component is influenced, and a slightly different predicted shear strength is obtained based on Tsai-Wu criterion applied to the matrix.

It deserves a special mentioning on the thermal residual stresses. Due to difference in both the mechanical and thermal properties of the fiber and matrix, and due to almost always existed difference between a processing and a working temperatures, thermal residual stresses occur in the fiber and matrix of almost every composite. Even for a thermal set resin composite cured at room temperature, heat will release during the resin curing which results in the thermal residual stresses. In the previous work^[8], the thermal residual stresses were said to have insignificant effect on the composite strength behavior. Why such a different conclusion exists, although the calculations for those stresses are the same? The reason is the involvement of a SCF. As seen from **Table 2**, the SCFs for the composite systems under consideration are near to or greater

than 2. This means that the calculated thermal residual stresses should be around doubly amplified. The significance of these amplified stresses thus results.

However, even in the simplest case where linearly elastic matrix properties are employed throughout and no thermal residual stresses are incorporated, the present predictions have still reached an overall accuracy level comparable to that of Zinoviev et al.'s predictions.

6. Conclusion

The ultimate strength of a laminated composite subjected to any load can be reasonably well predicted based on the Bridging Model using independently measured constituent properties only. It is the incorporation of a SCF that makes this prediction reasonable. Matrix inelasticity and thermal residual stresses are two other important factors to influence the accuracy of a composite strength prediction. Different failure criteria should be applied to assess failure status of a different constituent. All of the Bridging Model formulae involved are explicit and in closed-form, and are very convenient as a design tool. The present work is useful to the composite community for much more effective and expanded use of composite structures as well as for from constituent bottom up to final structure design using composite materials. As long as a material database for all of the possible constituent properties is established, the design and development of a composite structure can be achieved with no experiments on the composite itself any more. This will not only save lots of money cost, but also significantly speed up the output of the composite structure.

Acknowledgement

Financial supports from the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 11272238), Doctoral Fund of Ministry of Education of China (Grant No. 20120072110036) and the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (Grant No. 1330-219-104) are acknowledged.

References

1. Z.-M. Huang "Simulation of the mechanical properties of fibrous composites by the bridging micromechanics model". *Compos Part A*, Vol. 32, No. 2, pp. 143-172, 2001.
2. Z.-M. Huang, YX Zhou "Strength of Fibrous

Composites". Zhejiang University Press & Springer, Hangzhou & Heidelberg, 2011.

3. S. Ryan S, M. Wicklein, A. Mouritz, W. Riedel, F. Schäfer, K. Thoma "Theoretical prediction of dynamic composite material properties for hypervelocity impact simulations". *Int. J. Impact Engng.*, Vol. 36, pp. 36: 899-912, 2009.
4. YX Zhou, Z.-M. Huang. "A modified ultimate failure criterion and material degradation scheme in bridging model prediction for biaxial strength of laminates". *J Compos Mater.*, Vol. 42, No. 20, pp. 2123-2141, 2008.
5. S. P. Timoshenko, J. N. Goodier. "*Theory of Elasticity*". New York: McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1970.
6. S. Cheng, D. Chen. "On the Stress Distribution in Laminae". *J Reinf Plast Compos.* Vol. 7, No. 2, pp. 136-144, 1988.
7. L. Liu , Z.-M. Huang. "Stress concentration factor in matrix of a composite reinforced with transversely isotropic fibers", *J. Comp. Mater.* (in press)
8. Z.-M. Huang. "A bridging model prediction of the ultimate strength of composite laminates subjected to biaxial loads". *Compos Sci Tech.* Vol. 64, No. 3-4, pp. 395-448, 2004.
9. P. D. Soden, M. J. Hinton, A. S. Kaddour . "Lamina properties, lay-up configurations and loading conditions for a range of fibre-reinforced composite laminates". *Compos Sci Tech.* Vol. 58, No. 7, pp. 1011-1022, 1998.
10. P. D. Soden, M. J. Hinton, A. S. Kaddour. "Biaxial test results for strength and deformation of a range of E-glass and carbon fibre reinforced composite laminates: failure exercise benchmark data". *Compos Sci Tech.* Vol. 62, No. 12-13, pp. 1489-1514, 2002.
11. P. A. Zinoviev, S. V. Grigoriev, O. V. Lebedeva, L. P. Tairova. "The strength of multilayered composites under a plane-stress state". *Compos Sci Tech.* Vol. 58, No. 7, pp. 1209-1223, 1998.
12. M. J. Hinton, A. S. Kaddour, P. D. Soden. "A further assessment of the predictive capabilities of current failure theories for composite laminates: comparison with experimental evidence". *Compos Sci Tech.* Vol. 64, No. 3-4, pp. 549-588, 2004.
13. M. J. Hinton, A. S. Kaddour, P. D. Soden. "A comparison of the predictive capabilities of current failure theories for composite laminates, judged against experimental evidence". *Compos Sci Tech.* Vol. 62, No. 3-4, pp. 1725-1797, 2002.

Appendix

$$[S_{ij}^m] = \begin{cases} [S_{ij}^m]^e, & \text{when } \sigma_e^m \leq \sigma_Y^m \\ [S_{ij}^m]^e + [S_{ij}^m]^p, & \text{when } \sigma_e^m > \sigma_Y^m \end{cases}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$[S_{ij}^m]^e = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E^m} & -\frac{\nu^m}{E^m} & 0 \\ & \frac{1}{E^m} & 0 \\ \text{symmetric} & & \frac{1}{G^m} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$[S_{ij}^m]^p = \frac{9}{4M_T^m(\sigma_e^m)^2} \times \begin{bmatrix} (\sigma_{11}^m)^m (\sigma_{11}^m)^m & (\sigma_{22}^m)^m (\sigma_{11}^m)^m & 2(\sigma_{12}^m)^m (\sigma_{11}^m)^m \\ & (\sigma_{22}^m)^m (\sigma_{22}^m)^m & 2(\sigma_{12}^m)^m (\sigma_{22}^m)^m \\ \text{symmetry} & & 4(\sigma_{12}^m)^m (\sigma_{12}^m)^m \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\sigma_e^m = \sqrt{(\sigma_{11}^m)^2 + (\sigma_{22}^m)^2 - (\sigma_{11}^m)(\sigma_{22}^m) + 3(\sigma_{12}^m)^2}, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$M_T^m = \frac{E^m E_T^m}{E^m - E_T^m}, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$(\sigma_{11}^m)^m = (2\sigma_{11}^m - \sigma_{22}^m)/3, \quad (\sigma_{22}^m)^m = (2\sigma_{22}^m - \sigma_{11}^m)/3, \\ (\sigma_{12}^m)^m = \sigma_{12}^m. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$[A_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ 0 & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ 0 & 0 & a_{33} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$a_{11} = E_m / E_{11}^f, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$a_{22} = \beta + (1 - \beta) \frac{E_m}{E_{22}^f}, \quad 0 < \beta < 1,$$

$$\beta = 0.35 \sim 0.45 \text{ in general}, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$a_{33} = \alpha + (1 - \alpha) \frac{G_m}{G_{12}^f}, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1,$$

$$\alpha = 0.35 \sim 0.45 \text{ in general}, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$E_m = \begin{cases} E^m, & \text{when } \sigma_e^m \leq \sigma_Y^m \\ E_T^m, & \text{when } \sigma_e^m > \sigma_Y^m \end{cases}, \quad (\text{A.11})$$

$$G_m = \begin{cases} 0.5E^m / (1 + \nu^m), & \text{when } \sigma_e^m \leq \sigma_Y^m \\ E_T^m / 3, & \text{when } \sigma_e^m > \sigma_Y^m \end{cases}, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$a_{12} = \frac{(S_{12}^f - S_{12}^m)(a_{22} - a_{11}) + (S_{22}^m - S_{22}^f)a_{21}}{S_{11}^m - S_{11}^f}, \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$a_{13} = \frac{d_2 \beta_{11} - d_1 \beta_{21}}{\beta_{11} \beta_{22} - \beta_{12} \beta_{21}}, \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$a_{23} = \frac{d_1 \beta_{22} - d_2 \beta_{12}}{\beta_{11} \beta_{22} - \beta_{12} \beta_{21}}, \quad (\text{A.15})$$

$$d_1 = (a_{11} - a_{33})S_{13}^m,$$

$$d_2 = (V_f + V_m a_{11})(a_{22} - a_{33})S_{23}^m + (V_f + V_m a_{33})a_{12}S_{13}^m,$$

$$\beta_{11} = S_{12}^m - S_{12}^f, \quad \beta_{12} = S_{11}^m - S_{11}^f,$$

$$\beta_{22} = (V_f + V_m a_{22})(S_{12}^m - S_{12}^f),$$

$$\beta_{21} = V_m (S_{12}^f - S_{12}^m)a_{12} - (V_f + V_m a_{11})(S_{22}^f - S_{22}^m). \quad (\text{A.16})$$

In the above, E^m , G^m , and ν^m are the Young's modulus, shear modulus, and Poisson's ratio of the matrix material respectively, σ_Y^m is its yield strength, and E_T^m is a hardening modulus (tangent to a tensile or compressive stress-strain curve) of the matrix.

Table 2. Properties of four used UD laminae

Property	AS4/3501-6	T300/BSL914C	E-glass/LY556 /HT907/DY063	E-Glass / MY750 /HY917/DY063 epoxy
Fiber volume fraction $V_f(\%)$	0.6	0.6	0.62	0.6
Curing temperature T_0 (°C)	177	120	120	120
Working temperature $T_1(\text{°C})$	25	25	25	25

α	0.3	0.35	0.35	0.35
β	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
K^I	1.3038	1.3128	1.4756	1.4727
K^{II}	1.3934	1.4056	1.6907	1.6634
K	1.8166	1.8453	2.4949	2.4497

Table 3. Properties of constituent materials of four used laminae

Property	AS4/3501-6		T300/BSL914C		E-glass/LY556		E-Glass/MY750	
	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix
E_{11} (GPa)	225	4.2	230	4.0	80	3.35	74	3.35
E_{22} (GPa)	15	4.2	15	4.0	80	3.35	30.8	1.24
ν_{12}	0.2	0.34	0.2	0.35	0.2	0.35	30.8	1.24
G_{12} (GPa)	15	1.567	15	1.418	33.33	1.24	0.2	0.35
G_{23} (GPa)	7	1.567	7	1.418	33.33	1.24	30.8	1.24
$(\sigma\gamma)_1$ (MPa)		38.1		41.6		31.9		32.6
$(\sigma\gamma)_2$ (MPa)		41.8		49.6		38.4		39.9
$(\sigma\gamma)_3$ (MPa)		46.1		55.8		44.7		46.8
$(\sigma\gamma)_4$ (MPa)		50.1		59.9		49.9		52.0
$(\sigma\gamma)_5$ (MPa)		54.0		63.1		53.6		55.6
$(\sigma\gamma)_6$ (MPa)		57.6		66.3		56.1		58.0
$(\sigma\gamma)_7$ (MPa)		61.2		68.9		58.1		60.1
$(\sigma\gamma)_8$ (MPa)		64.6		71.4		60.0		62.0
$(E_T)_1$ (MPa)		4200		4000		3350		3350
$(E_T)_2$ (MPa)		2507		2015		1566		1698
$(E_T)_3$ (MPa)		2530		1384		1337		1387
$(E_T)_4$ (MPa)		2072		769		944		918
$(E_T)_5$ (MPa)		1721		548		584		542
$(E_T)_6$ (MPa)		1409		457		338		317
$(E_T)_7$ (MPa)		1202		324		245		244
$(E_T)_8$ (MPa)		991		275		197		186
$\sigma_{u,t}$ (MPa)	3205.9 /3216.5 ^a	69	2462 /2471.8	75	1804.1 /1808.9	80	2091.7 /2097.3	80
$\sigma_{u,c}$ (MPa)	2458.6 /2438.3	250	1499.4 /1482.8	150	908.9 /898.1	120	1314.1 /1303.4	120
S_u (MPa)	---	50	---	70	---	44.73 /34.7 ^b	---	54 ^c
$\alpha_{11}(10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C})$	-0.5	45	-0.7	55	4.9	58	4.9	58
$\alpha_{22}(10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C})$	15	45	12	55	4.9	58	4.9	58
$\alpha_{12}(10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C})$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

^a retrieved from lamina tensile or compressive strength with (before slash “/”) and without (after slash “/”) thermal residual stresses taken into account;

^b retrieved from an in-plane shear strength of the lamina with (before slash “/”) and without (after slash “/”) thermal residual stresses taken into account;

^c taken from provided data for the WWFE-II (the second world-wide failure exercise) with the same material system.

Table 4. Grades obtained with different solution schemes

(LMP=linear matrix property used, NLMP= non-linear matrix property used, NT=without thermal stresses, WT=with thermal stresses)

	Zinoviev	Huang(retrieved) (NLMP & WT)	Huang(provided) with SCFs (LMP & NT)	Huang(provided) with SCFs (NLMP & NT)	Huang(provided) with SCFs (NLMP & WT)
Grade A	53	57	50	58	72
Grade-B	43	45	45	46	36
Grade C	29	23	30	21	17
A+B	96	102	95	104	108
A/Total	42.4%	45.6%	40.0%	46.4%	57.6%
A+B/Total	76.8%	81.6%	76.0%	83.2%	86.4%

Fig. 5. Comparison between predictions and experiments for a UD composite